

Dual Band Microstrip Patch Antenna for IEEE802.11b Application

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Abstract : In this paper, the design of a coaxial feed single layer rectangular microstrip patch antenna for IEEE802.11b application is presented. The proposed antenna is designed by using substrate FR4_epoxy having permittivity of about 4.4 and tangent loss of 0.013. The substrate are designed and to evaluate the performance of modeled antenna using HFSS v.11 EM simulator, from Ansoft . The proposed antenna dual resonant frequency have been achieved in the band of 1.57GHz-1.68GHz(with BW 30 MHz) and 2.25 GHz -2.55GHz(with BW 40MHz).The simulation results with frequency response, radiation pattern and return loss ,VSWR, Input Impedance are presented with appropriate table and graph

Keywords : — Microstrip, Radiation Pattern, Return Loss, Tangent Loss, VSWR.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014